

Surgery

Non-arbitrary minimum threshold of yearly performed pancreatoduodenectomies: national multicentric study.

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	YMSY-D-20-00113R2
Article Type:	Original Communication
Section/Category:	Clinical
Keywords:	Duodenopancreatectomy
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Manuscript Region of Origin:	SPAIN
Abstract:	<p>Background Annual hospital volume of pancreatoduodenectomies (PD) could influence postoperative outcomes. The aim of this study is to establish with a non-arbitrary method the minimum threshold of yearly performed PD in order to improve several postoperative quality outcomes.</p> <p>Method Prospective follow-up of patients submitted to PD in participating hospitals during 1 year. The influence of hospital volume on quality outcomes was analyzed by uni and multivariable model. The minimum threshold of yearly performed PD in order to improve outcomes was established by Akaike's information criteria.</p> <p>Results Data from 877 patients operated in 74 hospitals were analyzed. Out of 12 quality outcomes, 9 were influenced by hospital PD volume on multivariable analysis. To decrease the risk of complications and the risk of retrieving an insufficient number of lymphnodes at least 31 PD/year should be performed. To decrease the risk of prolonged length of stay, postoperative death and affected surgical margins at least 37, 6 and 14 PD/year should be performed respectively.</p> <p>Conclusion Several postoperative quality outcomes are influenced by the number of yearly performed PD and could be improved by establishing a minimum threshold of procedures. Number of procedures needed to improve quality outcomes has been established by a non-arbitrary method.</p>

To,

The Editor

Surgery

Dear Sir/Madam,

We are submitting the manuscript titled: "Non-arbitrary minimum threshold of yearly performed pancreatoduodenectomies: national multicentric study." under the original article category for consideration towards publication in your esteemed journal. This article will not be sent to another journal until a decision is made concerning publication by Surgery. I accept to undertake full responsibility for authorship during the submission and review stages of the manuscript. The manuscript has been seen and approved by all authors.

Thanking you in anticipation,

Yours Sincerely,

Dimitri Dorcaratto MD., Ph.D.

Reviewer #1:

This work has relevance in that, as opposed to most database studies in the literature, more variables are captured and analyzed supporting the importance of higher volume to improve outcomes following PD. The revisions add important details and the discussion is much more concise.

We would like to thank the reviewer for this comment and for the opportunity to improve our study.

Reviewer #4:

The revision of this article is improved but still some important aspects are not clearly shown in the tables. The explanation and use of the Akaike's information criteria (AIC) is helpful but please also use or start with the standard general used criteria as used in most studies

Thanks to the reviewer to give us the opportunity to improve our work. We performed several changes based on your new suggestions which are extensively discussed below and outlined in the text. We hope that the manuscript is now meeting the required qualities for publication in Surgery.

So the suggestion:

Start in table 1 patients characteristics to include also the suppl table 1 part of the characteristics (not the outcome part here as now include in the suppl table)

Based on the reviewer suggestion we modified Table 1. We included perioperative characteristics of patients from the 4 subgroups and we eliminated the outcomes variables which are now showed in a different table.

Next in table 2 include / summarize also outcome data for the same different groups (as used in table 1) as well include mortality of the different groups. Mortality should be included here. There must be a reason not be too clear about mortality of subgroups !!!

We created a new Table (supplementary Table 1) as indicated by the reviewer. It includes the univariate comparison of the quality outcomes among the 4 arbitrary established volume groups. We changed the Method and Results section of the article accordingly.

“Perioperative characteristics of included patients were initially compared among four arbitrary “a priori” established hospitals groups (<10 PD-year; 10-20 PD-year; 21-30 PD-year and >30 PD-year). Chi square and ANOVA test, or their non-parametric equivalent, were used to compare categorical and continuous variables respectively among the four groups (Table 1 and Supplementary Table 1).”

Mortality has been included in results tables since the first version of the manuscript. Clavien 5 patients are patients who died during the postoperative period secondary to complications. We understand that this information was not explained in the text with enough clarity and therefore we added the following sentence in the Definitions section of Material and Methods:

“Patients who died during postoperative follow-up were included in Clavien 5 group.”

In table 2 the authors presented An Univariable analysis of the influence of annually performed PD (pancreatoduodenectomies) on postoperative quality outcomes. But this is a "misleading" table comparing only hospital with annual volume cut-off from the lowest (2 cases/year) to the highest (44 cases/year)

We are very sorry for the misunderstanding on this very important point of our work. The univariable analysis showed in Table 2 includes all 74 hospitals which participated in the study. They have been dichotomized in two groups with different cut-offs for every outcome based on AIC. Therefore, not “only hospital with annual volume cut-off from the lowest (2 cases/year) to the highest (44 cases/year)” have been compared. All hospitals included in the study have been compared. This is what we consider the most important point in our work: for every quality outcome we found (using the previously validated AIC method) a different volume cut-off which best explain differences among hospitals on that particular outcome. That is why we respectfully think that Table 2 and 3 (univariate and multivariate analysis based on AIC criteria cut-offs) should not be substituted by univariate and multivariate analysis comparing hospital groups based on arbitrarily established cut-offs (as the ones we used in the new versions of Table 1 and Suppl Table 1). We think that this is exactly what differentiates our work from most previously published works on volume influence on surgical outcomes. Moreover, we are convinced that this is the method that should be used to establish minimal hospital volumes to improve quality outcomes. However, if the reviewer and the editor disagree on this point, we can perform a traditional univariate and multivariate analysis comparing results among arbitrary established hospital groups. We fear that this would rest originality and, especially, usefulness to our investigation.

Please remove this one and include with criteria as mentioned above the new table 2

Based on the reviewer suggestion we included the univariate comparison of quality outcome among arbitrary established hospital groups in Suppl Table 1.

Next step is the Univariable and multivariable analysis of the entire group

As suggested by the reviewer univariate comparison of the results among hospitals has been performed both in Suppl Table 1 (arbitrary established groups) and Table 2 (AIC established groups). Multivariable analysis has been performed in Table 3 for AIC established groups. We think that adding a multivariate analysis to again compare the same outcomes among arbitrary established groups (<10, 10-20 and 21-30 PD per year) would maybe create an excess of redundant information for the reader. However, if the reviewer and the editor think that this information is necessary, we will be happy to create a supplementary Table 3 showing it.

The results section should be shortened all data are provided in the tables

Based on this suggestion and on the previous comments by the reviewer, we restructured and shortened the Results section of the manuscript (from 546 words to 425). The Results section has been changed as follows:

“Demographic and perioperative variables analyzed in the study are summarized in Table 1 and supplementary Table 1. During the study period, data from 877 patients operated in 74 hospitals had been collected. The median number of patients operated yearly by each centre was 19 with an IQR of 14-28. Of these patients, 532 (60,7%) presented postoperative complications. Of the 62 patients who died during the study period 4 (6,5%) presented only medical complications, 16 (26%) presented only surgical complications and 42 (67,5%) had both surgical and medical complications. Of the 118 (13,5%) patients who needed to be reoperated due to surgical complications 51 (43,2%) had a postoperative pancreatic fistula; 51 (43,2%) had intrabdominal hemorrhage; 15 (12,7%) had biliary fistula; 9 (7,6%) had pancreatitis of the pancreatic remnant; 20 (16,9%) had wound infection; 6 (5,1%) had evisceration and 20 (16,9%) presented intrabdominal abscess. As expected, patients operated in facilities with a >30 PD-year volume tended to be younger, to receive more preoperative chemotherapy, to have more pancreatic adenocarcinoma and less benign lesions or ampullary tumors and to present more venous involvement.

The results of univariable and multivariable models performed to analyze the influence of yearly case volume on surgical outcomes are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. Figure 1 represents the value of AIC depending on the annual procedure volume that was used to establish the optimal volume cut-off for every quality outcome based on multivariable approach. On univariable analysis (Table 2), performing more than 37 cases/year decreased by 64% the risk of prolonged hospital stay; performing more than 31 cases/year decreased by 62% the risk of reoperation, by 63% the risk of surgical complications, by 50% the risk of medical complications, by 60% the risk of general complications and augmented more than 3 times the possibility of resecting more than 12 lymphnodes; performing more than 14 cases/year decreased by 49% the risk of R1 resection. Furthermore, mortality risk decreased by 54% in hospitals that performed more than 6

PD/year. However, performing more than 21 cases/year, more than doubled the risk of hospital readmission. Multivariable analysis (Table 3) confirmed that hospital volume decreased the risk of prolonged postoperative stay; postoperative surgical complications, medical complications; general complications; the risk of R1 resection; the risk of postoperative death and increased the possibility of retrieving more than 12 lymphnodes. Furthermore, hospitals that performed more than 31 cases/year also had a 47% decrease in the risk of severe postoperative complications on multivariable analysis. The number of performed cases did not confirm its influence on the risk of reoperation and PPF.”

Considering the use of the above mentioned tables the discussion needs to be adapted

The results of the study have been fully discussed in the Discussion of the article based on the reviewer indications:

“...the volume cut-offs considered in previous studies were almost always arbitrarily established, most of the time using quartile or quintile distribution of the cases. Previous publications demonstrated that arbitrarily established volume cut-offs, even if statistically significant, are less precise than empirically established ones in determining the real number of procedures needed in order to achieve better outcomes...”

“...Based on the results of the current study, 9 out of 12 important quality outcomes seem to be influenced by the number of PD performed annually by each hospital. Importantly, this influence proved to be independent from confounding factors such as age, gender, ASA score, preoperative biliary drain use, preoperative chemo and/or radiotherapy use, type of performed resection, superior mesenteric or portal vein resection, type of pancreatic anastomosis, use of surgical drains and type of resected neoplasm...”

“...this is the first work to establish the non-arbitrary volume cut-off needed to improve the results of several post-PD quality outcomes....”

1 **Non-arbitrary minimum threshold of yearly performed**
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3 **pancreatoduodenectomies: national multicentric study.**
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9 Francisco Sanchez-Bueno⁸, Francisco Botello-Martinez⁹ and Luis Sabater², on
10 behalf of the Pancreatoduodenectomy Multicentric Spanish Group
11 investigators*.
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56 * The Pancreatoduodenectomy Multicentric Spanish Group investigators are
57 co-authors of this study and are listed in Appendix S1 (supporting information).
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Abstract

Background

Annual hospital volume of pancreatoduodenectomies (PD) could influence postoperative outcomes. The aim of this study is to establish with a non-arbitrary method the minimum threshold of yearly performed PD in order to improve several postoperative quality outcomes.

Method

Prospective follow-up of patients submitted to PD in participating hospitals during 1 year. The influence of hospital volume on quality outcomes was analyzed by uni and multivariable model. The minimum threshold of yearly performed PD in order to improve outcomes was established by Akaike's information criteria.

Results

Data from 877 patients operated in 74 hospitals were analyzed. Out of 12 quality outcomes, 9 were influenced by hospital PD volume on multivariable analysis. To decrease the risk of complications and the risk of retrieving an insufficient number of lymphnodes at least 31 PD/year should be performed. To decrease the risk of prolonged length of stay, postoperative death and affected surgical margins at least 37, 6 and 14 PD/year should be performed respectively.

Conclusion

Several postoperative quality outcomes are influenced by the number of yearly performed PD and could be improved by establishing a minimum threshold of procedures. Number of procedures needed to improve quality outcomes has been established by a non-arbitrary method.

Introduction

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2 Periapillary neoplasms settle in an area of great anatomical complexity
3 and their management implies difficult surgical procedures such as
4 pancreatoduodenectomy (PD). Postoperative morbidity and mortality rates after
5 PD are as high as 68% and 8% ^{1 2}. However, these results could be biased by
6 the fact that most publications come from high-volume teaching centers, while
7 pancreatic resections are performed also by low-volume centers in most
8 European countries ^{2 3}. Postoperative complications have a negative impact not
9 only on patients' quality of life and hospital costs, but also on long-term
10 oncological outcomes ^{4 5}. Several authors have stressed the correlation
11 between hospital surgical procedure volume and postoperative morbidity and
12 mortality rates ^{1 3 6-12}. Furthermore, other important quality outcomes such as
13 postoperative length of stay, readmission rates, surgical resection margins
14 involvement or number of retrieved lymphnodes could be related to hospital
15 procedures volume ^{1 12}. However, these factors have rarely been investigated
16 as outcomes in order to establish quality standards after PD together with
17 morbidity and mortality rates.

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31 Currently, most of the publications on the relation between quality
32 outcomes and hospital PD volume are based on retrospective reviews of private
33 or public nationwide databases subjected to coding and time-range biases.
34 Furthermore, the attempt to establish a minimal hospital volume for pancreatic
35 resections has mainly been based on arbitrary cut-offs ^{11 12}. The minimal
36 volume threshold necessary to accomplish several quality outcomes for
37 pancreatic oncological surgery should be established in a large cohort of
38 patients with the participation of high-volume and low/medium-volume hospitals
39 ¹³. This could avoid some of the biases caused by most publications based on
40 the analysis of the experience of high volume reference centers or of large
41 national databases and could allow a snapshot of the "real-life" results of
42 pancreatic surgery in a European country.

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52 The aim of the current study is to establish the minimal number of PD needed
53 by a hospital to accomplish some quality standards in oncological pancreatic
54 surgery.
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Methods

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4 A multicentric prospective national study was promoted by the
5 Hepatobiliary Department of the Spanish Surgical Association with the intention
6 of retrieving data from Spanish hospitals where PD were performed over a
7 period of one year. All members of the Spanish Surgical Association were
8 contacted by e-mail to participate in the study. Inclusion criteria were: patients
9 who underwent open PD to treat suspected periampullary neoplasm between
10 January 1st and December 31st 2015. Exclusion criteria were: patients who
11 underwent emergency PD for any reason, patients who underwent other
12 pancreatic resections different from PD and laparoscopic PD. Variables were
13 collected using the online platform www.typeform.com and processed using
14 Microsoft Excel, version 12.3.6, 2008 (Microsoft Corporation, One Microsoft
15 Way, Redmond, WA 98052-7329, USA). Every center was responsible for the
16 correct collection of their variables. Preoperative patient assessment methods,
17 the need for preoperative histopathological confirmation of periampullary
18 neoplasm, the need of preoperative biliary drain placement and the need for
19 preoperative chemo/radiotherapy and surgical indications were decided by each
20 participating center following their own clinical protocols.
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34 Included patients signed an informed consent for the anonymous use of
35 their demographic data following the current Spanish law on digital data
36 protection.
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Variables

42 The following variables were collected in the database, analyzed and
43 used as independent variables in multivariable analysis: age; gender; American
44 Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) score; preoperative biliary drainage
45 (endoscopic or percutaneous); preoperative chemo and/or radiotherapy; type of
46 resection (classical PD or pylorus preserving PD); venous (superior mesenteric
47 or portal) resection; type of pancreato-enteric anastomosis performed
48 (pancreato-jejunostomy, pancreato-gastrostomy, pancreatic remnant sealing);
49 use of surgical drains; type of resected neoplasm (pancreatic adenocarcinoma,
50 cholangiocarcinoma, duodenal adenocarcinoma, other pancreatic malignancies,
51 chronic pancreatitis, ampullary neoplasm, neuroendocrine tumor, benign
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1 tumor); surgical margin involvement; number of retrieved lymphnodes
2 (dichotomized as >or< 12 lymphnodes); postoperative pancreatic fistula (PPF);
3 90-day morbidity and mortality; postoperative surgical and medical
4 complications; reoperation; length of hospital stay; hospital readmission; annual
5 hospital PD volume.
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10 Definitions

11 Pancreato-gastric and pancreto-jejunal anastomoses included any type
12 of anastomosis between the pancreas and the stomach or the jejunum
13 respectively, depending on surgeon preference. PPF was defined using the
14 International Study Group on Pancreatic Surgery (ISGPS) updated definition ¹⁴
15 and graded as B or C depending on its clinical impact. Postoperative
16 complications were defined as any deviation from the normal postoperative
17 course within 90 days after PD and their severity was graded using the Dindo-
18 Clavien Classification ^{15 16}. **Patients who died during postoperative follow-up**
19 **were included in Clavien 5 group.** Surgical complications included PPF; delayed
20 gastric empty (ISGPS definition)¹⁷; endoluminal or intraperitoneal haemorrhage
21 (ISGPS definition) ¹⁸; biliary fistula (International Study Group of Liver Surgery
22 definition) ¹⁹; wound infection (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
23 definition) ²⁰; surgical site infection (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
24 definition) ²⁰; intraperitoneal abscess (Centers for Disease Control and
25 Prevention definition)²⁰; peritonitis (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
26 definition)²⁰. Length of hospital stay was calculated from the day of surgical
27 intervention to the day of hospital discharge and included the length of any
28 hospital readmission during the first 90 days after surgery. Surgical margin
29 involvement was defined as the presence of neoplastic cells within 1 mm
30 distance from any of the surgical margins ^{21 22}.
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50 Statistical analysis

51 Descriptive statistics were presented as median and IQR interquartile range
52 (IQR) for continuous variables. The absolute number of patients and associated
53 percentage was used for categorical variables.
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58 Based on previous publications ^{2 13}, the following variables were chosen as
59 outcomes in order to establish the quality standards of pancreatic resection and
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1 used as dependent variables: length of postoperative hospital stay; PPF rates
2 and grade; reoperation rates; 90-day postoperative morbidity rates;
3 postoperative complication type (surgical or medical); severe (Clavien >II)
4 postoperative complications rates; 90-day postoperative mortality rates; number
5 of retrieved lymphnodes; R0 resection margins rates and readmission rates.
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9 Perioperative characteristics of included patients were initially compared
10 among four arbitrary “a priori” established hospitals groups (<10 PD-year; 10-20
11 PD-year; 21-30 PD-year and >30 PD-year). Chi square and ANOVA test, or
12 their non-parametric equivalent, were used to compare categorical and
13 continuous variables respectively among the four groups (Table 1 and
14 Supplementary Table 1).
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18 Generalized linear model from Binomial family and log link were carried out
19 from a univariable and multivariable perspective. Univariable analyses were
20 performed using each of the aforementioned variables as dependent variable
21 and the number of performed PD by each hospital during the study period as
22 independent variable. Based on previous publications ²³⁻²⁵, Akaike’s information
23 criteria (AIC) was then used to establish which number of cases/year best fitted
24 to explain the variation of each outcome. AIC examines the amount of
25 information contained in a model based on the likelihood of the data observed
26 given the model under consideration, penalizing the excess of predictors
27 included in the model ²⁶. It therefore allows estimating the usefulness of each
28 independent variable to explain the variations of the dependent variable in a
29 model. In the case of the current work, AIC was sequentially performed for
30 every annual volume cut-off from the lowest (2 cases/year) to the highest (44
31 cases/year) in order to understand which volume cut-off best explained the
32 difference of the observed outcomes both in univariable and multivariable
33 analysis. Although the absolute level of AIC is not informative, lower values
34 imply better model adjustment.
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51 Each dependent variable was then analyzed in a multivariable model. The
52 event risk for dependent variables was expressed as Odds Ratio (OR) and 95%
53 confidence intervals (CI). AIC was again sequentially performed for every
54 annual volume cut-off for each outcome. The model in which the OR for the
55 analyzed outcome variable was significant and with the lowest AIC was chosen
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as the model that better explained the outcome variation and the minimal volume cut-off was therefore established.

The following factors were controlled for in the multivariable model as possible confounders together with the aforementioned dependent variables (outcomes): age; gender; ASA; preoperative biliary drainage; preoperative chemo and/or radiotherapy; type of resection; venous resection; type of pancreatic anastomosis; use of surgical drains; type of resected neoplasm.

A p value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. R version 3.5.1 (The R Foundation for Statistical Computing, www.r-project.org) was used for statistical analysis.

Results

Demographic and perioperative variables analyzed in the study are summarized in Table 1 and supplementary Table 1. During the study period, data from 877 patients operated in 74 hospitals had been collected. The median number of patients operated yearly by each centre was 19 with an IQR of 14-28. Of these patients, 532 (60,7%) presented postoperative complications. Of the 62 patients who died during the study period 4 (6,5%) presented only medical complications, 16 (26%) presented only surgical complications and 42 (67,5%) had both surgical and medical complications. Of the 118 (13,5%) patients who needed to be reoperated due to surgical complications 51 (43,2%) had a postoperative pancreatic fistula; 51 (43,2%) had intrabdominal haemorrhage; 15 (12,7%) had biliary fistula; 9 (7,6%) had pancreatitis of the pancreatic remnant; 20 (16,9%) had wound infection; 6 (5,1%) had evisceration and 20 (16,9%) presented intrabdominal abscess. As expected, patients operated in facilities with a >30 PD-year volume tended to be younger, to receive more preoperative chemotherapy, to have more pancreatic adenocarcinoma and less benign lesions or ampullary tumors and to present more venous involvement.

The results of univariable and multivariable models performed to analyze the influence of yearly case volume on surgical outcomes are summarized in Tables 2 and 3. Figure 1 represents the value of AIC depending on the annual procedure volume that was used to establish the optimal volume cut-off for

1 every quality outcome based on multivariable approach. On univariable
2 analysis (Table 2), performing more than 37 cases/year decreased by 64% the
3 risk of prolonged hospital stay; performing more than 31 cases/year decreased
4 by 62% the risk of reoperation, by 63% the risk of surgical complications, by
5 50% the risk of medical complications, by 60% the risk of general complications
6 and augmented more than 3 times the possibility of resecting more than 12
7 lymphnodes; performing more than 14 cases/year decreased by 49% the risk of
8 R1 resection. Furthermore, mortality risk decreased by 54% in hospitals that
9 performed more than 6 PD/year. However, performing more than 21
10 cases/year, more than doubled the risk of hospital readmission. Multivariable
11 analysis (Table 3) confirmed that hospital volume decreased the risk of
12 prolonged postoperative stay; postoperative surgical complications, medical
13 complications; general complications; the risk of R1 resection; the risk of
14 postoperative death and increased the possibility of retrieving more than 12
15 lymphnodes. Furthermore, hospitals that performed more than 31 cases/year
16 also had a 47% decrease in the risk of severe postoperative complications on
17 multivariable analysis. The number of performed cases did not confirm its
18 influence on the risk of reoperation and PPF.

36 Discussion

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40 Annual hospital procedure volume has been appointed as one of the
41 factors which could influence short and long term outcomes after several major
42 surgical resections of abdominal cancers ^{10 27 28}. PD is a very demanding
43 surgical procedure and represents the only chance of cure for patients with
44 periampullary neoplasms ²⁹. Despite increasing evidence indicating that hospital
45 volume could influence the results after PD and that centralization of pancreatic
46 surgery may lead to decreased postoperative mortality and improved oncologic
47 outcomes ^{1 3 6-9 11 12 23 30 31}, most European countries have not yet implemented
48 a minimal case-load regulation and PD is performed in both high and low
49 volume hospitals. There are several limitations shared by most of the current
50 publications investigating the relationship between hospital procedure volume
51 and postoperative outcomes in pancreatic surgery. Firstly, most data comes

1 from retrospective reviews of private or public insurance databases which are
2 prone to several important coding biases, usually include patients operated over
3 a long period of time, and are often unable to retrieve all the variables that
4 should be used in multivariable models as possible confounding factors for
5 surgical outcomes ^{1 7 32}. Secondly, the volume cut-offs considered in previous
6 studies were almost always arbitrarily established, most of the time using
7 quartile or quintile distribution of the cases ^{3 12}. Previous publications
8 demonstrated that arbitrarily established volume cut-offs, even if statistically
9 significant, are less precise than empirically established ones in determining the
10 real number of procedures needed in order to achieve better outcomes ³³.
11 Thirdly, only one outcome has been commonly considered for establishing
12 quality criteria (ie: usually postoperative mortality or more rarely morbidity) ^{7 9}.
13 The current work aimed to overcome the aforementioned limitations. First, it is a
14 prospective follow-up of all PDs performed in 74 hospitals over a short period of
15 time, which can give an accurate snap-shot of the current real-life situation of
16 pancreatic surgery in a European country where centralization has not yet been
17 implemented. Second, a previously validated empirical method (AIC) to
18 establish non-arbitrary volume cut-offs which significantly influence surgical
19 outcomes has been used ²³⁻²⁶. Last, based on previous publications ^{2 13},
20 several outcomes were considered in order to study the quality of surgical
21 results. In our opinion, limiting the evaluation of the outcomes of PD only to
22 postoperative mortality or crude morbidity risks of oversimplifying a complex
23 evaluation process. Based on the results of the current study, 9 out of 12
24 important quality outcomes seem to be influenced by the number of PD
25 performed annually by each hospital. Importantly, this influence proved to be
26 independent from confounding factors such as age, gender, ASA score,
27 preoperative biliary drain use, preoperative chemo and/or radiotherapy use,
28 type of performed resection, superior mesenteric or portal vein resection, type
29 of pancreatic anastomosis, use of surgical drains and type of resected
30 neoplasm. These findings are very important because, to our knowledge, this is
31 the first work to establish the non-arbitrary volume cut-off needed to improve the
32 results of several post-PD quality outcomes. AIC test results indicated that the
33 annual case-volume that better explained postoperative surgical, medical,
34 general and severe complications variations and the increased number of
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1 retrieved lymphnodes during surgery was 31 PD-year. The volume that better
2 explained the variation of the hospital length of stay was a little higher (37
3 cases-year). Only 14 and 6 cases/year were necessary in order to explain
4 differences in the R0 resection and postoperative mortality rates respectively.
5 Although appealing, it is overly simplistic to expect to find a single volume cut-
6 off which could fit several different quality outcomes. Our results suggest that
7 complication rates and number of retrieved lymphnodes, which are both related
8 to surgical technique and perioperative patient management factors such as the
9 presence of dedicated endoscopic, interventional radiology or intensive care
10 units and the use of modern neoadjuvant therapies, have a similar volume
11 threshold. Postoperative length of stay, which could be influenced by some
12 additional variables such as enhanced recovery programs which are
13 implemented, for PD, only in high volume hospitals, showed a higher threshold.
14 However, the rate of R0 resection, which is mostly influenced by surgeon
15 experience more than by hospital volume and structure, has a lower quality cut-
16 off. The risk of postoperative death was significantly decreased in hospitals
17 reaching a lower cut-off (6 or more PD-year). Interestingly, PPF rates were not
18 influenced by surgical volume in our study. We hypothesize that this result could
19 be explained by the strong influence of other important risk factors on PPF such
20 as patient characteristics, tumor type and pancreatic parenchyma firmness.
21 However, we cannot exclude a type II error caused by the relative reduced
22 number of events. In the current study, readmission rates were increased in
23 high volume centers. We can speculate that this interesting finding could be
24 related with the higher healthcare pressure suffered by high volume centers,
25 which, on one side could stimulate shorter length of stay, but on the other can
26 augment the risk of high readmission rate. The difference in volume cut-offs
27 between postoperative morbidity and mortality deserves further discussion and
28 could be explained by the low incidence of postoperative death when compared
29 to postoperative complications. Observing the AIC curve for postoperative
30 mortality, Figure 1 shows a low AIC value for the volume cut-off of 31 PD/year,
31 apart from the previously mentioned cut-off of 6. However, the 31 PD/year cut-
32 off was only nearly significant to discriminate hospitals with higher or lower
33 mortality rates [OR 0.33; CI 0.09-0.93; p=0.058]. As previously reported ³³, for
34 those surgical interventions in which mortality rates are relatively low (such as
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1 PD in our series) it is very difficult to find statistically significant differences on
2 a limited cohort of patients due to error type II. This could explain the difference
3 in volume cut-offs between morbidity and mortality outcomes. Even so, the
4 results of the mortality analysis are very important, because they establish a
5 minimal limit of 6 yearly performed PD which should not be crossed in order to
6 avoid a 68% increase in mortality rates. Based on the results of the current
7 study it seems reasonable to propose that, in order to improve most quality
8 outcomes of PD in our environment, hospitals should perform at least 30 PD per
9 year. However, we acknowledge that it is overly simplistic to consider annual
10 volume as a stand alone variable which can explain the results of several
11 quality outcomes without be influenced by other modifiable factors such as the
12 presence of dedicated multidisciplinary teams or the implementations of
13 perioperative protocols for the optimization of complex patients.
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23 It is difficult to compare our results with previous publications because,
24 as mentioned earlier, most papers used arbitrary cut-offs to establish the
25 definition of high and low-volume centers. Other authors who used statistical
26 methodologies similar to the ones used in this paper to establish the threshold
27 of annual volume included pancreatic resections other than PD, therefore
28 finding different cut-offs for acceptable results ^{3 23}.
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34 However, when comparing the quality outcomes analyzed in the current
35 work with previously published large series ¹², we found that all of them met the
36 benchmarks established for PD in a recently published work by Sanchez-
37 Velazquez et al ². These acceptable results could nevertheless be improved by
38 centralization policies, given the results of the current study.
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43 One of the main limitations of this study is the relatively low number of
44 included patients, when compared with some national database reviews
45 published during the last decade. As previously mentioned, this could be the
46 cause of a type II error. However, significant differences in 9 important quality
47 outcomes have been showed in the current work using a validated and solid
48 statistical model. Some confounders for surgical outcomes such as patients'
49 body mass index, pancreatic tenderness, Wirsung duct diameter or estimated
50 blood loss could not be retrieved from participating centers and were omitted
51 from multivariate analysis, possibly influencing the study results. The
52 investigation of the effect of individual surgeons' volume on quality outcomes
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1 was beyond the objective of the current work. Surgeon volume influences
2 surgical outcomes probably less than the volume of the whole hospital, as
3 previously published ³⁴. However, we acknowledge that surgeon volume and
4 experience could be another possible source of bias of our work. Lastly, the
5 current study lacks the appropriate long term follow up to analyze oncological
6 results, which could also be influenced by hospital volume as suggested by
7 other authors ³⁵.
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12 Despite the previously mentioned defects, the results of this multicentric
13 follow-up of 877 patients submitted to PD in 74 Spanish hospitals are clear:
14 hospital procedure volume does influence most of the quality outcomes of PD
15 and a minimum annual volume threshold should be established to improve
16 them. Arbitrarily established volume cut-offs carry the risk of not accurately
17 reflecting the reality of European health care system and, in our opinion, they
18 should be substituted by statistically established cut-offs. Furthermore, future
19 studies should consider including multiple quality outcomes in order to have a
20 more complete understanding of the relationship between hospital procedure
21 volume and PD results.
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31 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

32 The authors thank Ms. Landy Menzies for language assistance in revising the
33 English of the manuscript.
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40 **Conflicts of interest**

41 None of the authors of the article declares any conflict of interest.
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44 **Funding**

45 The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or
46 publication of this article.
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Bibliografy

1. Kutlu OC, Lee JE, Katz MH, Tzeng CD, Wolff RA, Varadhachary GR, et al. Open Pancreaticoduodenectomy Case Volume Predicts Outcome of Laparoscopic Approach: A Population-based Analysis. *Ann Surg* 2018;267(3):552-60.
2. Sanchez-Velazquez P, Muller X, Malleo G, Park JS, Hwang HK, Napoli N, et al. Benchmarks in Pancreatic Surgery: A Novel Tool for Unbiased Outcome Comparisons. *Ann Surg* 2019;270(2):211-18.
3. Krautz C, Nimptsch U, Weber GF, Mansky T, Grutzmann R. Effect of Hospital Volume on In-hospital Morbidity and Mortality Following Pancreatic Surgery in Germany. *Ann Surg* 2018;267(3):411-17.
4. Dorcaratto D, Mazzinari G, Fernandez M, Munoz E, Garces-Albir M, Ortega J, et al. Impact of Postoperative Complications on Survival and Recurrence After Resection of Colorectal Liver Metastases: Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ann Surg* 2019;270(6):1018-27.
5. Sandini M, Ruscic KJ, Ferrone CR, Qadan M, Eikermann M, Warshaw AL, et al. Major Complications Independently Increase Long-Term Mortality After Pancreatoduodenectomy for Cancer. *J Gastrointest Surg* 2019;23(10):1984-90.
6. Adam MA, Thomas S, Youngwirth L, Pappas T, Roman SA, Sosa JA. Defining a Hospital Volume Threshold for Minimally Invasive Pancreaticoduodenectomy in the United States. *JAMA Surg* 2017;152(4):336-42.
7. Alsfasser G, Leicht H, Gunster C, Rau BM, Schillinger G, Klar E. Volume-outcome relationship in pancreatic surgery. *Br J Surg* 2016;103(1):136-43.
8. Balzano G, Zerbi A, Capretti G, Rocchetti S, Capitanio V, Di Carlo V. Effect of hospital volume on outcome of pancreaticoduodenectomy in Italy. *Br J Surg* 2008;95(3):357-62.
9. de Wilde RF, Besselink MG, van der Tweel I, de Hingh IH, van Eijck CH, Dejong CH, et al. Impact of nationwide centralization of pancreaticoduodenectomy on hospital mortality. *Br J Surg* 2012;99(3):404-10.
10. Finks JF, Osborne NH, Birkmeyer JD. Trends in hospital volume and operative mortality for high-risk surgery. *N Engl J Med* 2011;364(22):2128-37.
11. Hata T, Motoi F, Ishida M, Naitoh T, Katayose Y, Egawa S, et al. Effect of Hospital Volume on Surgical Outcomes After Pancreaticoduodenectomy: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Ann Surg* 2016;263(4):664-72.
12. van der Geest LG, van Rijssen LB, Molenaar IQ, de Hingh IH, Groot Koerkamp B, Busch OR, et al. Volume-outcome relationships in pancreatoduodenectomy for cancer. *HPB (Oxford)* 2016;18(4):317-24.
13. Sabater L, Garcia-Granero A, Escrig-Sos J, Gomez-Mateo Mdel C, Sastre J, Ferrandez A, et al. Outcome quality standards in pancreatic oncologic surgery. *Ann Surg Oncol* 2014;21(4):1138-46.
14. Bassi C, Marchegiani G, Dervenis C, Sarr M, Abu Hilal M, Adham M, et al. The 2016 update of the International Study Group (ISGPS) definition and grading of postoperative pancreatic fistula: 11 Years After. *Surgery* 2017;161(3):584-91.
15. DeOliveira ML, Winter JM, Schafer M, Cunningham SC, Cameron JL, Yeo CJ, et al. Assessment of complications after pancreatic surgery: A novel grading system applied to 633 patients undergoing pancreaticoduodenectomy. *Ann Surg* 2006;244(6):931-7; discussion 37-9.

16. Dindo D, Demartines N, Clavien PA. Classification of surgical complications: a new proposal with evaluation in a cohort of 6336 patients and results of a survey. *Ann Surg* 2004;240(2):205-13.
17. Wente MN, Bassi C, Dervenis C, Fingerhut A, Gouma DJ, Izbicki JR, et al. Delayed gastric emptying (DGE) after pancreatic surgery: a suggested definition by the International Study Group of Pancreatic Surgery (ISGPS). *Surgery* 2007;142(5):761-8.
18. Wente MN, Veit JA, Bassi C, Dervenis C, Fingerhut A, Gouma DJ, et al. Postpancreatectomy hemorrhage (PPH): an International Study Group of Pancreatic Surgery (ISGPS) definition. *Surgery* 2007;142(1):20-5.
19. Koch M, Garden OJ, Padbury R, Rahbari NN, Adam R, Capussotti L, et al. Bile leakage after hepatobiliary and pancreatic surgery: a definition and grading of severity by the International Study Group of Liver Surgery. *Surgery* 2011;149(5):680-8.
20. Berrios-Torres SI, Umscheid CA, Bratzler DW, Leas B, Stone EC, Kelz RR, et al. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention Guideline for the Prevention of Surgical Site Infection, 2017. *JAMA Surg* 2017;152(8):784-91.
21. Sabater L, Gomez-Mateo Mdel C, Lopez-Sebastian J, Munoz-Fornier E, Morera-Ocon F, Cervantes A, et al. Prognostic implications of the standardized study of resection margins in pancreatic cancers. *Cir Esp* 2014;92(8):532-8.
22. Verbeke CS. Resection margins and R1 rates in pancreatic cancer--are we there yet? *Histopathology* 2008;52(7):787-96.
23. Meguid RA, Ahuja N, Chang DC. What constitutes a "high-volume" hospital for pancreatic resection? *J Am Coll Surg* 2008;206(4):622 e1-9.
24. Chang C, Hsieh MK, Chang WY, Chiang AJ, Chen J. Determining the optimal number and location of cutoff points with application to data of cervical cancer. *PLoS One* 2017;12(4):e0176231.
25. Kim SG, Nagao M, Nozawa M, Doi T. Optimal cutoff score for patient-reported outcome measures after anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction using load-displacement curve analysis. *J Orthop Surg (Hong Kong)* 2019;27(3):2309499019887581.
26. Akaike H. A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 1974;19(6):716-23.
27. Coupland VH, Lagergren J, Luchtenborg M, Jack RH, Allum W, Holmberg L, et al. Hospital volume, proportion resected and mortality from oesophageal and gastric cancer: a population-based study in England, 2004-2008. *Gut* 2013;62(7):961-6.
28. Mamidanna R, Ni Z, Anderson O, Spiegelhalter SD, Bottle A, Aylin P, et al. Surgeon Volume and Cancer Esophagectomy, Gastrectomy, and Pancreatectomy: A Population-based Study in England. *Ann Surg* 2016;263(4):727-32.
29. Tempero MA. NCCN Guidelines Updates: Pancreatic Cancer. *J Natl Compr Canc Netw* 2019;17(5.5):603-05.
30. Alsfasser G, Kittner J, Eisold S, Klar E. Volume-outcome relationship in pancreatic surgery: the situation in Germany. *Surgery* 2012;152(3 Suppl 1):S50-5.
31. Gooiker GA, Lemmens VE, Besselink MG, Busch OR, Bonsing BA, Molenaar IQ, et al. Impact of centralization of pancreatic cancer surgery on resection rates and survival. *Br J Surg* 2014;101(8):1000-5.

- 1 32. Topal B, Van de Sande S, Fieuws S, Penninckx F. Effect of centralization of
2 pancreaticoduodenectomy on nationwide hospital mortality and length of stay.
3 *Br J Surg* 2007;94(11):1377-81.
- 4 33. Christian CK, Gustafson ML, Betensky RA, Daley J, Zinner MJ. The Leapfrog
5 volume criteria may fall short in identifying high-quality surgical centers. *Ann*
6 *Surg* 2003;238(4):447-55; discussion 55-7.
- 7 34. Schmidt CM, Turrini O, Parikh P, House MG, Zyromski NJ, Nakeeb A, et al. Effect
8 of hospital volume, surgeon experience, and surgeon volume on patient
9 outcomes after pancreaticoduodenectomy: a single-institution experience. *Arch*
10 *Surg* 2010;145(7):634-40.
- 11 35. Lidsky ME, Sun Z, Nussbaum DP, Adam MA, Speicher PJ, Blazer DG, 3rd. Going
12 the Extra Mile: Improved Survival for Pancreatic Cancer Patients Traveling to
13 High-volume Centers. *Ann Surg* 2017;266(2):333-38.

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Figure 1. Relation between Akaike's information criteria (AIC) values (Y axis) and hospital annual volume of performed pancreatoduodenectomies cut-offs (PD, X axis). The minimum AIC level indicates the optimal number of PD performed each year that better explains the variation of every outcome parameter (prolonged hospital stay, surgical complications, medical complications, general complications, severe complications, mortality, retrieved lymphnodes, R1 resection, readmission) adjusted by age; gender; ASA; preoperative biliary drainage; preoperative chemo and/or radiotherapy; type of resection; venous resection; type of pancreatic anastomosis; use of surgical drains; type of resected neoplasm.

Table 1. Demographic, Clinical and Perioperative Characteristics of Patients Undergoing Pancreaticoduodenectomy during the study period. Hospitals have been divided in 4 groups based on annual volume.

Number of yearly performed PD		All facilities	<10 cases/year	10-20 cases/year	21-30 cases/year	>30 cases/year	p
		877 patients	117 patients	389 patients	193 patients	178 patients	
Characteristics		No.(% ^a)	No.(% ^a)	No.(% ^a)	No.(% ^a)	No.(% ^a)	
Median age (IQR)		67 (58-73)	68 (35-83)	67 (19-84)	67 (34-81)	64 (20-86)	0.003
Male gender		509 (58)	65 (55)	234 (60.1)	109 (56.4)	106 (59.5)	0.93
ASA	I	47 (5.4)	10 (8.5)	20 (5.1)	6 (3.1)	11 (6.2)	0.06
	II	408 (46.5)	51 (43.6)	187 (48.1)	87 (45.1)	82 (46.1)	
	III	373 (42.5)	49 (42)	160 (41.1)	96 (49.7)	69 (38.8)	
	IV	31 (3.5)	7 (6)	19 (4.9)	3 (1.6)	2 (1.1)	
Preoperative biliary drain	None	477 (54.3)	64 (55)	223 (57.3)	110 (57)	77 (43.2)	0.85
	Endoscopic Pecutaneous	296 (33.7) 96 (10.9)	41 (35) 13 (11)	139 (35.7) 27 (6.9)	66 (34.2) 18 (9.3)	57 (32) 47 (26)	
Preoperative chemotherapy		45(5.1)	11 (9.1)	16 (4.1)	5 (2.6)	13 (7.3)	0.023
Preoperative radiotherapy		24 (2.7)	5 (4.2)	9 (2.3)	3 (1.5)	7 (3.9)	0.35
Resection type	PD	692 (78.9)	96 (82)	304 (78.1)	158 (81.9)	134 (75.3)	0.26
	PPPD	174 (19.8)	19 (16.2)	81 (20.8)	32 (16.6)	42 (23.6)	
Venous resection		107 (12.2)	5 (4.2)	53 (13.6)	22 (11.3)	27 (15.1)	0.027
Pancreatic anastomosis	Pancreato-jejunostomy	722 (82.3)	91 (77.7)	318 (81.7)	156 (80.8)	157 (88.2)	0.43
	Pancreato-gastrostomy	135 (15.4)	24 (20.5)	63 (16.2)	30 (15.5)	19 (10.7)	
	Remnant sealing	15 (1.7)	2 (1.7)	6 (1.5)	6 (3.1)	1 (0.6)	
Surgical drains		709 (80.8)	112 (95.7)	384 (98.7)	193 (100)	175 (98.3)	0.08
Type of resected neoplasm	Pancreatic adenocarcinoma	424 (48.3)	46 (39.3)	207 (53.2)	78 (40.4)	93 (52.2)	0.005
	Cholangiocarcinoma	85 (9.7)	10 (8.5)	41 (10.5)	20 (10.4)	14 (7.9)	
	Duodenal adenocarcinoma	24 (2.7)	3 (2.6)	13 (3.3)	1 (0.5)	7 (3.9)	
	Other malignancies	20 (2.3)	8 (6.8)	6 (1.5)	7 (3.6)	7 (4)	
	Chronic pancreatitis	39 (4.4)	5 (4.3)	19 (5)	8 (4.1)	7 (4)	
	Ampullary neoplasm	132 (15.1)	25 (21.4)	56 (14.4)	31 (16.1)	20 (11.2)	

Neuroendocrine tumor	35 (4)	6 (5.1)	9 (2.3)	8 (4.1)	11 (6.2)
Benign tumor	72 (8.2)	14 (11.9)	21 (5.3)	27 (13.9)	9 (5)
Others	37 (4.2)	0	12 (3.1)	10 (5.2)	8 (4.4)

IQR: Interquartile Range; ASA: American Society of Anaesthesiologists score; PD: Pancreatoduodenectomy; PPPD: Pylorus Preserving Pancreatoduodenectomy. a Percentages may not add up to 100% owing to missing data.

Table 2. Univariable analysis of the influence of annually performed PD (pancreatoduodenectomies) on postoperative quality outcomes.

Outcome	Number of yearly performed cases (established by AIC)	Low volume hospitals N(%)	High volumen hospitals N(%)	OR	IC	p
Prolonged hospital stay ^a	37	401 (48.7)	11 (25.6)	0.36	0.17-0.70	0.004
PPF grade B/C	NA					
Reoperation	31	112 (14.4)	6 (6.1)	0.38	0.14-0.82	0.02
Surgical POC	31	493 (63.4)	39 (39.4)	0.37	0.24-0.57	0.1 ⁻⁶
Medical POC	31	269 (34.6)	21 (21.2)	0.50	0.30-0.82	0.008
General POC	31	539 (69.3)	47 (47.5)	0.40	0.26-0.61	0.1 ⁻⁵
Severe POC ^b	NA					
Postoperative death	6	7 (9.2)	55 (6.9)	0.46	0.24-0.95	0.02
Retrieved Lymphnodes ^c	31	470 (63.3)	86 (87.8)	4.16	2.32-8.14	0.1 ⁻⁶
R1 resection	14	68,9 (28.6)	100,9 (17)	0.51	0.34-0.74	0.0005
Readmission	21	34 (6.9)	48 (14.7)	2.32	1.46-3.72	0.0003

^a Hospital stay>15 days; ^b Dindo-Clavien>II; ^c >12 lymphnodes; AIC: Akaike's information criteria; OR: Odds Ratio; IC: 95% Confidence Interval; PPF: Postoperative Pancreatic Fistula; NA: not available (no threshold of minimal performed PD/year found for this outcome); POC: Postoperative Complications.

Table 3. Summary of multivariable analysis of the influence of annually performed PD (pancreatoduodenectomies) on postoperative quality outcomes.

Outcome	Number of yearly performed cases (established by AIC)	OR	IC	p
Prolonged hospital stay ^a	37	0.77	0.67-0.88	0.04
PPF grade B/C	NA			
Reoperation	NA			
Surgical POC	31	0.32	0.20-0.52	0.4 ⁶
Medical POC	31	0.86	0.78-0.95	0.005
General POC	31	0.79	0.71-0.88	0.9 ⁵
Severe POC ^b	31	0.53	0.27-0.97	0.05
Postoperative death	6	0.32	0.15-0.74	0.005
Retrieved Lymphnodes ^c	31	3.94	2.07-8.2	0.7 ⁵
R1 resection	14	0.60	0.39-0.92	0.02
Readmission	21	2.25	1.31-3.91	0.003

^a Hospital stay > 15 days; ^b Dindo-Clavien > II; ^c > 12 lymphnodes; AIC: Akaike's information criteria; OR: Odds Ratio; IC: 95% Confidence Interval; PPF: Postoperative Pancreatic Fistula; NA: not available (no threshold of minimal performed PD/year found for this outcome); POC: Postoperative Complications.

Supplementary Table 1. Postoperative quality outcomes after pancreatoduodenectomy according to arbitrary established hospital groups.

Number of yearly performed PD		All facilities	<10 cases/year	10-20 cases/year	21-30 cases/year	>30 cases/year	p
		877 patients	117 patients	389 patients	193 patients	178 patients	
Quality outcomes		No.(%^a)	No.(%^a)	No.(%^a)	No.(%^a)	No.(%^a)	
R1 resection		211 (24.1)	19 (16.2)	103 (26.4)	41 (21.2)	48 (26.9)	0.11
Number of retrieved lymphnodes (>12)		556 (63.4)	58 (49.5)	254 (65.2)	121 (62.6)	132 (74.1)	0.01
PPF	None	690 (78.7)	90 (76.9)	304 (78.1)	148 (76.7)	148 (83.1)	0.56
	Biochemical leak	92 (10.5)	11 (9.4)	48 (12.3)	20 (10.4)	13 (7.3)	
	B	53 (6)	8 (6.8)	19 (4.9)	16 (8.3)	10 (5.6)	
	C	42 (4.8)	8 (6.8)	18 (4.6)	9 (4.7)	7 (3.9)	
Postoperative complications	None	345 (39.3)	54 (46.2)	145 (37.3)	62 (32.1)	84 (47.2)	0.037
	Clavien I	118 (13.5)	8 (6.8)	65 (16.7)	18 (9.3)	27 (15.2)	
	Clavien II	217 (24.7)	28 (23.9)	92 (23.7)	64 (33.2)	33 (18.5)	
	Clavien IIIa	42 (4.8)	5 (4.3)	16 (4.1)	10 (5.2)	11 (6.2)	
	Clavien IIIb	58 (6.6)	11 (9.4)	24 (6.2)	12 (6.2)	11 (6.2)	
	Clavien IVa	23 (2.6)	2 (1.7)	11 (2.8)	7 (3.6)	3 (1.7)	
	Clavien IVb	12 (1.4)	2 (1.7)	6 (1.5)	3 (1.6)	1 (0.6)	
	Clavien V	62 (7.1)	7 (6)	30 (7.7)	17 (8.8)	8 (4.5)	
Postoperative complications type	Surgical	532 (60.7)	63 (58.8)	244 (62.7)	131 (67.8)	94 (52.8)	0.01
	Medical	290 (33.1)	40 (34.1)	118 (30.3)	81 (41.9)	51 (28.6)	
Reoperation		118 (13.5)	19 (16.2)	49 (12.6)	30 (15.5)	20 (11.2)	0.47
LHS (> 15 days)		412 (47)	59 (50.4)	190 (48.8)	91 (47.1)	72 (40.4)	0.05
Readmission		82 (9.4)	5 (4.2)	28 (7.1)	36 (18.6)	13 (7.3)	0.04

R1: Neoplastic involvement of the surgical margin; PPF: Postoperative Pancreatic Fistula; LHS: Length of Hospital Stay. a Percentages may not add up to 100% owing to missing data.

Appendix S1.

List of the the Pancreatoduodenectomy Multicentric Spanish Group Investigators.

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Article summary

After analyzing 877 duodenopancreatectomies performed in 74 hospitals we found that several quality outcomes are influenced by the number of yearly performed procedures. Necessary number of performed procedures to improve outcomes has been calculated. The importance of this finding is that the minimum number of performed pancreatoduodenectomies can be calculated to improve quality outcomes.

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